

CHEMICAL ACTIVITY OF HALOGEN DERIVATIVES OF SUBSTITUTED AMIDES OF MALONIC ACID. PART I. INTERACTION OF GRIGNARD'S REAGENT ON THE CHLORO DERIVATIVES OF SUBSTITUTED AMIDES OF MALONIC ACID

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The following dichloro derivatives of the substituted amides of malonic acid have been interacted with the Grignard's reagent *viz.* phenyl magnesium bromide and benzyl magnesium chloride.

(1) Dichloromalondi-phenylamide. (2) Dichloromalondi-*p*-tolylamide. (3) Dichloromalondi-*o*-tolylamide
(4) Dichloromalondi-*r*:*s*:*4*-xylylamide.

Contrary to expectations, instead of ditertiary alcohols, monochloro derivatives of the following type were obtained, from the above substances *viz.*

The investigations embodied herein were undertaken with a view to throwing some light on the interaction taking place between the Grignard reagent and the chloro derivatives of the substituted amides of malonic acid. In previous work attention was mainly concentrated upon the reactivity of the hydrogen atoms of the methylene group situated between two carbonyl groups. Other centres of activity of the molecules of such substances have not been investigated up to now.

From the inspection of a structure such as (I) it will be seen that there are at least three points

of attack *viz.* :—

- (i) the hydrogen atoms of the methylene group,
- (ii) the hydrogen of the imino groups, and
- (iii) the carbonyl groups.

It may be assumed that substances having the structure (II) would present to the Grignard reagent points of attack at the carbonyl (CO) as well as at the imino (-NH-) groups. In the event of the carbonyl group reacting the compound (II) would be formed and if imino groups react, the course of reaction would be anticipated as follows :—

It has been found, however, that unreacted amide is obtained when malondiphenylamide and malondibenzylamide are reacted with phenyl magnesium bromide. The explanation of this inactivity may be sought in the influence of $-NHR-$ group in the case of the carbonyl groups and of $(-R-)$ radicals in the case of imino groups. According to the hypothesis of Vörländer, the atoms of a radical or those of a continuous system may exhibit an alternate polarity which may be symbolised by means of $\oplus$ and $\ominus$ signs, attached to the individual atoms. As such, the reacting amide may be represented as:—

It will be seen from the above that the radicals (C_6H_5), which are positive as a whole, induce a greater charge of opposite sign on the nitrogen of the imino groups; this increased negative charge on the nitrogen holds very firmly the hydrogen atom which itself is positively charged as to keep it hooked with a greater force than before, with the result that the hydrogen is rendered unreplaceable by the reagent. Consequently, the imino (NH) group, as a whole, becomes inactive. Again, the negatively charged nitrogen induces a higher positive polarity on the carbon atom of the carbonyl group; as a result, the negatively charged oxygen has to utilise all its negative polarity for being hooked on to the carbon atom with a greater force than before. It is, therefore, very unlikely that the oxygen atoms can possess any residual negative force which could induce the free valency of the fragment ($-\text{MgX}$) to attach to itself. This renders the carbonyl group also inactive towards the Grignard reagent.

The chloroderivatives of various amides of malonic acid are more reactive than the corresponding non-chlorinated substances and hence the following compounds have been selected for the investigation of their interaction with the Grignard's reagent:—

- (i) Dichloromalondiphenylamide ;
- (ii) Dichloromalondi-*p*-tolylamide ;
- (iii) Dichloromalondi-*o*-tolylamide ;
- (iv) Dichloromalondi-1 : 3 : 4 : 4'-xylylamide.

Dichloromalondiphenylamide reacts vigorously with phenyl magnesium bromide yielding colourless product (III), m.p. 176° .

The reaction product has been assigned the formula (III) because

(i) The chlorine atom could be reduced quantitatively by hydriodic acid generated from KI and KCl (Kurt Meyer, *Annalen*, 1911, 380, 212; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 951, 305).

(ii) On treatment of the product with sulphuryl chloride dichloromalondiphenylamide is obtained.

(iii) When the product is treated with aniline, it gives a product which is identical with the reaction product of monochloroethyl malonate and aniline.

The course of reaction can be explained by the following mechanism :

Such a mode of mechanism is not unusual in view of the fact that a similar reaction has been found to take place in the case of the semicarbazone of dimethylbutylacetophenone and Grignard's reagent (Biquard, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1938, 8, 209).

In attempting to knock off the second chlorine atom by using four molecules of the Grignard's reagent for every molecule of the dichloro derivative, it has been found out that the amide $\text{H}_2\text{C} : (\text{CONHR}')_2$ does not result but a very little quantity of the monochloro compound together with a large amount of uncrystallisable resinous mass is obtained.

The difference in the reactivity of the chlorine atoms in such dichloro derivatives is not unusual, as substantiated by the velocity of replacement of chlorine atom by hydrogen (*cf.* Part II of this series, *this issue*, p. 355).

The present investigation is of interest because some previous attempts made, as outlined under (i) and (ii) below, to obtain monochloro derivatives of the substituted amids of malonic acid did not give any conclusive results—

(i) The action of 1 molecule of sulphuryl chloride on the amide leads to a mixture of dichloro derivative and the original amide and not the monochloro compound.

(ii) Conrad and Bischoff tried to condense monochloro-ethyl malonate with aniline, probably in the hope of converting it into monochloromalondiphenylamide, but evidently they obtained the compound (IV).

